

FitSM - IT Service Management for federated human data nodes

[Richelle D. Björvang](#)¹, [Erik Hedman](#)¹, [Markus Englund](#)¹ and [Owen Appleton](#)²

¹National Bioinformatics Infrastructure Sweden, Science for Life Laboratory, Department of Cell and Molecular Biology, Uppsala University ²Swiss Institute of Bioinformatics - contact owen.appleton@sib.swiss

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Context

Introduction

This guide is intended to support groups in the federated human data area who are interested in implementing an IT Service Management (ITSM) framework to support their professional delivery of IT Services. Introducing ITSM can be challenging due to the unfamiliar terminology and concepts, so this guide attempts to make it more accessible, with links to supporting material. It was prepared as part of the ELIXIR Staff Exchange program between [NBIS National Bioinformatic Infrastructure Sweden](#) and [SIB Swiss Institute of Bioinformatics](#), which was on the same topic. It does not provide every answer needed to implement ITSM, but should offer a good starting point, initial orientation, and a set of suggestions for how to proceed.

Background

European and global research are on a trajectory from locally run technology products to widespread online services, often delivered by distributed communities to users at many different locations. This contrasts with the previous picture of more discrete tools, which were downloaded and run locally, on local data.

Such a shift moves operational responsibility from end users to technology and now service developers, ensuring that not only are services effective, but delivered in a way that makes them easy and realistic to use. This demands skills that research organisations often lack, particularly in areas such as continuous service operation, user management, and sustainable management of digital infrastructure.

IT Service Management and FitSM

ITSM as a discipline has developed over the last 30 years to support organisations in building, delivering, operating, and controlling IT services offered to customers. It is widely used across the commercial and public sectors to control services and ensure they are valuable for customers. In the commercial sector, this has led to complex best practice frameworks and standards for ITSM, which are effective but are poorly adopted by the academic and research sectors. They are too complex, heavyweight, and are written in a vocabulary that is not familiar or easy to adopt in academic research. As a result, traditional ITSM has been very poorly adopted in academia, even though the general trajectory of work in the sector increasingly requires the competencies and structures that ITSM provides.

[FitSM](#) was developed as part of an EU-funded research project (FedSM, 2012-2015) to create very lightweight ITSM approaches. These were intended to particularly support federated scenarios, academic centres, and SMEs, who were poorly served by traditional ITSM, but can be used in any service delivery context.

The FitSM standard family is open source and released using open licences. It is free to access and implement [all core documents](#); however, some costs may be incurred related to training and certification of personnel or services. Nevertheless, it remains the most cost-efficient way for organisations to access ITSM. FitSM has now been self-supporting for more than a decade and is managed by a non-profit, FitSM e.V., registered in Germany.

Direct needs for managed services

Along with the general move toward services, there are some specific needs for ITSM across emerging federated service infrastructures related to federated human data for research. The [European Genomic Data Infrastructure \(GDI\)](#) and the [Federated European Genome-phenome Archive \(FEGA\)](#) are two emerging platforms in the federated human data space, where nodes in multiple countries, not just in Europe but globally, must cooperate to deliver connected services. Alongside this, the [European Open Science Cloud \(EOSC\)](#) is a larger web of [Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable \(FAIR\)](#) data and services being built up with nodes across the continent. In all these cases, this requires service operators to align their practices across diverse countries, sectors, and locations. This is where FitSM can be of use. As a lightweight and open-source standard, it can be adopted partially or completely by nodes within a federation to ensure key processes, such as incident management (helpdesks) or service level management, deliver shared Service Level Agreements (SLAs).

FitSM is already specified as part of GDI to ensure that node helpdesks operate in a correct and comparable manner, and is also part of the [EOSC federation handbook](#) for delivering [EOSC nodes](#). This recognises that in providing professional services, especially delivering them across a federation, a shared and open framework is a strong requirement.

Implementing ITSM for federated human data with FitSM

This section of the document provides a set of steps that are commonly required in implementing ITSM in a provider, such as a federated human data node.

Figure 1. Overview of steps for ITSM implementation

Identify the need

The first step in considering the implementation of IT Service Management is to understand the driver or the need for the implementation, although in many cases, this may occur before people find this guide. The need for structured service management will typically drive the initial information gathering and training, and subsequently justify a mandate for implementation.

There are numerous reasons to implement ITSM, but in the context of federated human data, these may commonly include:

- Clarifying the services to be delivered and tying them to the needs of customers in research organisations and clinical settings. In the research sector, where development often begins in funded research projects, this is especially important, as insufficient user demand is a frequent criticism of research projects.
- Identifying the components and processes needed to deliver services, so that costs can be understood, and that sustainable funding to support components and processes can be secured. This supports operation beyond initial funding, in terms of budgeting and in justifying requests for additional funding or investment.
- Finding a common way to operate federated services and speaking the same language across multiple organisations and countries. It is important to adopt common procedures for key activities in support of service delivery, such as operating helpdesks, delivering agreed capacities and availability, or managing relationships with customers and suppliers.
- Demonstrating compliance with regulations. In the context of federated human data, these regulations are related to sensitive personal data handling enforced at national or European scales.

It is quite common that some selected staff receive initial FitSM training during this phase, either proactively or through another activity, which allows them to see the benefits of a structured approach and promote this internally within the node or organisation.

Define a goal and receive a mandate

With a clear need for a structured approach to service delivery and management hopefully agreed upon, there is a need to convert this into a clear goal for the first stage of implementation.

The first step in achieving this is to ensure a clear mandate from the top management of the organisation or federation in question. While IT service management can bring significant benefits and improvements, its introduction is a form of organisational change. Organisational change is often necessary but can be difficult and needs to be carefully planned and implemented under control. IT service management introduction will generate costs in several ways: in costs for training, in additional time needed to design and introduce new processes and structures, and in reduced capacity to do other work. The introduction should bring significant benefits, in cost savings or in improved efficiency, better delivery, and greater customer satisfaction, but this can take time to appear.

Buy-in, support, and engagement by top management are necessary to ensure that the plan can be supported and enforced. With any organisational change, there is a significant chance of resistance from staff, whether deliberate or not, and this is a key risk to implementation. Clear statements by top management and follow-up to ensure conformance to new processes are very important for successful IT service management implementation.

In federated human data nodes, there will often be some level of collaboration or federation in the delivery of services - either collaboration within, e.g., a country to provide a node to meet national needs, or collaboration between nodes to provide multinode, often international services. In these cases, a mandate and buy-in may not be to implement IT service management for a single organisation, but across a wider network. Such a framework is even more needed in these scenarios, as there is more complexity to be coordinated to deliver services. On the other hand, deploying some level of IT service management across a collaboration or federation is different from deploying for a single provider. In practice, all providers contributing to a node or larger federation will ultimately be better off if they adopt some structure for managing and delivering services. Still, it is unrealistic to ask all contributors to adopt ITSM to use it for their joint undertaking. In practice, the joint work will drive them to adopt some smaller elements of ITSM and start to think in processes and value-generating services, supporting the better management of the joint work and, at the same time, leading the participants toward more professional service delivery.

With a mandate in place, a goal for ITSM should be set. At this stage, it should not be too detailed, as it should be comprehensible to top management, who are unlikely to engage with the details of ITSM. Within a single organisation, this is often formulated as an IT Service Management Policy; however, in a federated scenario where it may be harder to get a 'policy' signed off, it could also be labelled as a high-level action plan.

Initial staff training and knowledge socialisation

Once a need is identified and a mandate from top management is given, the provider should seek out additional resources on IT service management, its benefits, risks, and implications. Introducing any form of management framework is a significant change for any organisation, and this requires careful consideration.

While organisations can conduct research into different options, the most effective way to understand IT Service management is to provide training for key staff. IT Service Management, like all management systems and standards, is complex. It includes a set of concepts and a specialist set of terminologies that are not always quickly accessible.

Additional Information

FitSM-0 Overview and vocabulary
Provides an overview of the FitSM process model and defines key IT Service Management terminology.

FitSM Foundation certification training provides an ideal path to inform organisations on IT Service Management, and to understand how it can be used, and what benefits it can bring. The FitSM foundation course is 1-1.5 days (depending on intensity) and can be delivered in person or online, in both cases followed by an online exam, leading to a formal certification supported by the market leader, APMG.

At the end of this course, participants are not only introduced to ITSM and the FitSM standard family, but will also be equipped with a shared vocabulary that allows them to describe and discuss professional service delivery. This facilitates socialisation of the understanding of ITSM across the organisation, and catalyses further internal conversations between staff on how services can and should be delivered and managed.

Understand the scope and services

Additional Information

FitSM-5 Guide - Identifying services

Explains services as bundles of value generating activities and components delivered together to address a customer need. Assists in defining what can, is and should be delivered as services.

With an understanding of ITSM and a shared conceptual framework and vocabulary for discussing it, the first priority is to identify the (initial) scope of the ITSM implementation. Defining a scope makes implementation more straightforward and realistic, reducing staff concern and workload, and increasing chances of success. The scope defines what will be under the control of the management system being

implemented, and often limits its initial applicability to, for example, certain customers, countries, locations, or services.

The last of these is typically the most important to define, and with it comes the need to determine the services offered by a provider or federation. This does not mean a need to 'start from scratch' with a provider's activities. Rather, it is redescribing the activities of a provider in a new context, one driven primarily by the customer perspective. Existing

activities should be gathered into value-generating bundles that address customer needs and are comprehensible to them. In general, this leads to a simplification to a smaller set of services built on top of a larger number of technical and other components, which do not all need to be public-facing.

The result of this phase of activity should be a clear set of initial services targeted to identified customers. These services will serve as the basis for building a Service Management System (SMS) to control, support, enable, and monitor their delivery.

Plan and implement selected processes

ITSM defines process models to divide the effort of delivering services into manageable chunks, each with clear goals, inputs, outputs, triggers, roles, responsibilities, and monitoring. Process models typically divide core work into 14-40 processes, with FitSM being the lowest end of the scale.

Processes exist to provide a framework on which activities can be hung, and to rationalise their interfaces and management. They range from strategic to operational, and from simple to very complex.

When deploying ITSM, all processes should ultimately be implemented, but not all at once. It is typical to start with a select number of key processes and to expand over time as the maturity of the SMS increases. An initial plan is to decide which processes are necessary at first. Some are likely to be universal for all providers, while others will be tailored to the particular situation of the provider and their customers. The likely processes needed are in a later section.

Additional Information

FitSM-1 Requirements

Defines 82 clear requirements to effectively manage delivery of services to your customers.

Additional Information

FitSM-3 Role model

Provides information on the key roles required for implementation of processes and the overall service management system.

The first step in implementation should be to assign responsibilities for key roles. While detailed documentation and guidance are eventually required, assigning responsibility tends to be the best first step in implementation. By assigning responsibility to someone with sufficient expertise for a role, you empower them to work out how the relevant process or activity can be executed, and this can then be documented based on experience.

Reflect, improve, and monitor

A key aspect of implementing ITSM is to adopt a strategy of continual improvement to service and service management. It is not possible, or at least realistic, to deploy an SMS in a single step, either in terms of effort or in terms of a tolerable pace of change for staff. ITSM advocates for constant but incremental change and improvement rather than 'big bang' change, as it is more effective and more acceptable to the staff.

At first, this reflection is based on setting out implementation plans, monitoring their execution, and adjusting plans to fit new facts or evidence. It is unlikely that the very first plans made will ultimately provide the best way to proceed, so flexibility must be allowed. The direction of improvement is typically more important than whether the precise steps to get there are those that were initially planned.

Once implementation becomes more mature, oversight moves from reconsidering plans to more operational monitoring of processes, based on performance indicators. Here, it is important to really understand the goal of the services, processes, and activities, and to consider how any given measure indicates effectiveness or efficiency in reaching that goal. There is a tendency in management systems to measure what can be easily measured, rather than what gives useful information on where things can be improved. Measurement is also potentially costly, so in general, new processes or services should only have a handful of measures or performance indicators defined. These can scale as the services, processes, and SMS do.

Ultimately, it is advisable to consider audits as an important aspect of maintaining and improving the quality of services and processes. Typically, these are thought of in the context of receiving an external certification for a provider or service, but are equally useful without this, as a way to get an impartial and somewhat external view on ITSM implementation to guide future development.

Additional Information

FitSM-6 Assessment and Audit tool
Assesses your compliance with FitSM, creates improvement plans, and prepares for organisational certification.

Key processes

All the processes in FitSM or any ITSM framework are ultimately required for full implementation, but some are more crucial than others in starting implementation. This section provides some information on key processes that are often implemented early in the introduction of ITSM.

Service Portfolio Management (SPM)

SPM is the most strategic process in IT Service Management, and almost always the first one that needs to be considered. ITSM is a service-oriented approach, and this requires an understanding of which services are delivered to customers.

On the other hand, this process is the one with the least well-defined inputs and step-by-step guidance, as it must synthesise a service portfolio from a combination of current activities, internal capacities, customer demands, market trends, and resource limitations.

This process is also complex, as in most cases, it is being applied to an already operating provider, who performs numerous activities that must be combined into services in the ITSM sense. The transition from existing activities and technical components to services can be challenging and typically benefits significantly from both training in an ITSM framework and often the support of some form of external advice. Often, what are initially presented as services are actually technical components, for instance, AAI or networks. While crucial, these are not the focus of customers; instead, supporting the services they care about, which might include things like image analysis or archiving a certain research data type.

Once an initial service portfolio is developed, activities can proceed to what promises are made about them and how these can be delivered, which is the topic of the following processes.

Service Level Management (SLM)

SLM is almost always the second process to be implemented, as it has two core functions: to maintain customer-facing service portfolios, and to manage agreements with customers and other stakeholders about services. Service catalogues are derived from the service portfolio, but are limited to what customers need to know about currently offered services. A catalogue is needed to engage with current and future customers.

Agreements about services are the second most important aspect needed in a new implementation of ITSM, after a clear idea of services coming out of SPM. The other ITSM

Additional Information

FitSM-2 Process activities and implementation

Provides details for initial and ongoing implementation of each process. Defines key questions and process interfaces.

processes subsequent to SLM essentially help you deliver on and improve on the agreements made under SLM about the services described in SPM.

As a first step, it is typically recommended to consider putting in place a generic (sometimes called corporate level) Service Level Agreement (SLA) to cover all services by the provider to all customers. Rather than getting into detailed per-service metrics, it should set out the general way services are delivered, including service times, support times, customer and provider responsibilities, reporting, information security, and other common aspects. This can later be supplemented with or replaced by service-level SLAs with more concrete promises.

SLAs are a commonly known tool in service delivery, but there tends to be an assumption that an SLA means very tight guarantees and financial penalties for failure to meet them. This may be true in some market sectors, such as telecommunications, but in research IT, it is not. Many services are provided without a charge based on funding body support, and customer expectations are not as high as in other sectors. It is typical to get resistance to SLAs, especially from legal or managerial staff in organisations, based on the assumptions above, but this should be addressed. While the research IT community has been historically tolerant of unclear service levels, this is reducing rapidly over time.

Customer and Supplier relationship management (CRM & SUPPM)

In almost all cases, one or both of the CRM and SUPPM processes will be important to implement early in the introduction of ITSM. FitSM, like all ITSM frameworks, has a strong focus on customer-orientation, driving service development, delivery, and improvement based on customer feedback and requests. CRM acts as a broad interface for all other processes to get this crucial customer feedback. Introducing CRM is important in moving this feedback collection from an unstructured to a structured activity, which many other processes rely on.

In many cases, Supplier Management (SUPPM) is not a high priority process for implementation, as it tends to be relatively straightforward, unless the provider has very significant external dependencies. However, in federated human data nodes, often services are provided through a federation of cooperating suppliers. In such cases, providers may choose to manage relationships with federation partners or key stakeholders, such as data providers, through the SUPPM process. In this case, this process provides a necessary mirror to the CRM process, but internal to the federation rather than outside of it.

Information Security Management (ISM)

All services should prioritise information security, but in federated human data nodes, this need is especially high. While security is an absolute that cannot be guaranteed, all service providers need to adequately address, manage, and control information security to fulfil their professional, ethical, and legal obligations. Data on information security management is also a crucial element to SLAs, and must be communicated to customers.

This process is likely to be the first implemented, which demands the creation of high-level policies, and perhaps the first that requires elements of risk management. Both of these functions will end up in use for other processes, but this is where the skills and structures to support them will be created.

The ISM process will therefore be a first example of the full chain of management activities, from setting a high-level information security policy with input from national and regional legislation, through defining risks to be addressed, to implementing specific controls to manage them. Apart from the content of the process itself, this will be an important milestone in moving to managed service delivery.

Incident and Service Request Management (ISRM)

The ISRM process primarily handles the helpdesk functions of a service provider, acting as a first point of contact for users and addressing their issues and enquiries. This process is perhaps most familiar to those who have not yet implemented ITSM, as some version of it is in place at all service providers. It is also a more well-defined, workflow-driven process, which involves a series of steps to go through to handle each ticket, whether it relates to an interruption of a service (incident) or a request for training or a new service (service request).

ISRM is also a place where the benefits of being more structured in other processes begin to show. For instance, in answering a helpdesk ticket, it can be correlated to a specific customer (managed via CRM) for a specific service (listed in SPM) based on a specific agreement (from SLM). ISRM is also the first of the more operational processes most organisations implement, and perhaps the most straightforward of them.

In a federated human data node, there will also potentially be a need to not only manage a helpdesk, but to federate the helpdesk functionality across a network. Here, it will be important to have a clear idea of what each provider does to manage incidents and service requests, so that it is possible to create structures for referring or escalating tickets between providers in the federation.

Change Management (CHM)

Change management is typically a more complex process and is rarely implemented early in ITSM implementation, as it requires other complex questions to be answered before it can be put into place. It is rarely recommended as an initial process, but in the case of federated human data nodes, there are drivers that may make it more urgent.

In federated situations, cooperating members of a federation must collaborate and interact in order to deliver services. This means that certain technical and other elements that are relied on by multiple federation partners must not be altered without consensus, notice, and discussion. In short, they must be under change control.

For federations, this often means a limited number of elements such as IPs, APIs, credentials, and standards, which are the touch points between partners. Full change management comes later, but this is a common pattern for federated providers.

Continual Service Improvement (CSI)

Finally, the CSI process is advisable for early implementation. Continual improvement is a basis for all ITSM, as an initial goal and an ongoing commitment. Creating a CSI process helps to socialise this way of thinking, and provides a path for feedback from all team members on how to improve and evolve services and service management.

Additional challenges in Federated scenarios

The trajectory of development above is a fairly generic one, and will apply to most new groups implementing ITSM, though some of the reflections included are more specific to federated scenarios. However, there are some additional challenges and situations that may be found more commonly where service providers are federated.

Perhaps the first of these to be seen in federations is a greater difficulty in establishing central authority and approval to implement ITSM. As described above, top management approval is crucial in the success of ITSM implementation. In a federation, there are many 'top managements' that must be convinced before management systems can be put in place.

On a related note, the approval to implement a management system in the research sector is often tied to a funded project, which requires one, rather than a push from an individual organisation to better manage services. In such cases, it is not uncommon for the project to provide a proxy for a wider mandate for implementation. Here, the risk is that the approval is tied only to the project, meaning it is hard to implement ITSM fully, or that the mandate fades with the project, and the implementation is not completed.

Where ITSM is implemented, there is a related tension between how much ITSM is or needs to be implemented at the nodes of a federation versus a central hub or organising body. In an ideal situation, all nodes would have ITSM frameworks in place, and then the central body would only need to bridge between them to give effective shared services. In practice, often the central body, while ultimately needing less complex ITSM implementation than the nodes, may find itself leading the nodes in implementation and maturity.

Finally, due to all the factors above, progress can be slower in federated scenarios, simply due to the added complexity they provide. However, these challenges can all be addressed, and typically, where there is a need to implement ITSM in a federation, there is also the drive to overcome them, as long as sufficient support is available.

Conclusion and next steps

This guide is an initial set of ideas on how to implement ITSM in a federated human data node, with guidance on the general context, steps to be taken, and recommendations on the processes to be implemented. This is intended as a quickstart guide to supporting ITSM implementation, supporting the requirements, and supporting material provided in the FitSM standard.

If the general approach presented here is followed, it will lead to sufficient maturity and initial success to support further development, as needed in the particular situation of that service provider. This can be continued using material from FitSM, or also drawing on information from other standards and frameworks, which are broadly compatible.

Much of the work implied here can be carried out by a provider, based on research into the concepts and structures proposed, but some may require external support. Training, at least, is both crucial and typically requires a third-party provider to support it. Consultancy may also be of use, especially with the early stages of implementation, including defining services and forming initial SLAs.

In general, this guide should help to bridge the gap between more structured material found in FitSM requirements and the narrative thread needed to instantiate them in support of a federated human data node.

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